

ANALYSIS OF *FKBP5* AND CORTISOL EXPRESSION IN PATIENTS UNDERGOING CHEMOTHERAPY

Muhammad Nouman Hasan¹, Muhammad Qasim Hasan², Arooj Khan³,
Muhammad Noman Tahir⁴, Muhammad Mustafa^{*5}

¹Kausar Abdulla Malik School of Life Sciences, Forman Christian College (A Chartered University), Lahore.

²Allama Iqbal Medical College – AIMC

³Kausar Abdulla Malik School of Life Sciences, Forman Christian College (A Chartered University) Lahore.

⁴Kausar Abdulla Malik School of Life Sciences, Forman Christian College (A Chartered University) Lahore.

⁵Aitchison College Lahore

^{*1}noumanhasan44@gmail.com, ²dr.qasimhassan22@gmail.com, ³aroojarif23@gmail.com,

⁴m.nomantahir99@gmail.com, ⁵muhammadmustafa25@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17404991>

Keywords

Article History

Received: 30 August 2025

Accepted: 08 September 2025

Published: 21 October 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Muhammad Mustafa

Abstract

Stress is a kind of important risk factor that leads towards the development and progression of major depression among the people. The *FKBP5* is an important gene that is important in stress response and Glucocorticoid Receptor (GR) signaling. It is a protein coding gene that belongs to the family of FK-506 protein, acts as co-chaperon which modulates the folding and activity of associated proteins. Keeping in view the importance and significance of *FKBP5*, I studied the exploration of the relatedness between cancer patients and *FKBP5* and evaluated the cortisol level in the serum of cancer patients and compared with control group. Blood samples were taken from cancer patients, which was followed by RNA extraction, cDNA synthesis and then evaluated its expression level. Quantitative PCR (qPCR) and Enzyme Linked Immune Sorbent Assay (ELISA) were then executed for quantification of gene expression and cortisol concentration in serum of patients and control group, respectively. Results indicate that data from gene expression and cortisol concentration comes from population that follows normal probability distribution. Apart from normality, no significance difference was found in *FKBP5* expression between cancer patients with respect to gender. In addition, no correlation was observed between *FKBP5* expression and cortisol concentration in the cancer patients. Keeping in mind significance and importance of *FKBP5*, it can be said that its product may be utilized in drug designing process for stress and cancer management.

INTRODUCTION

Stress is a type of important risk factor that leads towards the development and progression of major depression among the people (Ising *et al.*, 2019). The depression is a kind of relapsing disorder that affects most of the patients worldwide. Impaired stress response has been observed in patients after adverse experiences Environmental factors coupled with

genetics also contribute towards enhancement of depression risk and outcome developments (Kendler *et al.*, 2003). It causes lot of complications in body. To exemplify, stress and depression lead towards progression of cancer in patients. In addition, stress activated epigenetic regulations can augment to the severeness coupled with poor prognosis in cancer

patients (Fiaz *et al.*, 2022). Moreover, it has been indicated that stress can induce the cardiomyopathy in post-menopausal women (Ueyama *et al.*, 2008). Furthermore, evidence indicates that psych-social factors together with stress act as risk factor in development of hypertension (Spruill, 2013).

Furthermore, the concept that cancer and stress are linked has dominated lay discourse for so many years. Studies show that stress can gradually smoothen cancer progression through modulation of certain molecular pathways required for indication of cancer (Eckerling *et al.*, 2021). Since stress is a part of our lives, chronic stress like depression, anxiety and loneliness can adversely affect human health. It is also observed that it can lead towards development and progression of tumor. Stress hormone induced the development and promotion of cancer through molecular pathways such as p53 degradation, inducing DNA damage and regulation of tumor microenvironment. It can also stimulate inflammatory reactions and network between inflammatory cellular entities and cancer affected cells to make the inflammatory network of tumor microenvironment. In this way it promotes all stages of tumor progression and metastasis (Dai *et al.*, 2020). It is thought that cancer arising with ageing show increase in oxidative stress (Benz & Yau, 2008). In addition, psychological factors can be considered as the major contributor in the treatment of cancer. This field makes the oncologist focused on the development of such pathway as directed at the problems of cancer affected people and education at all levels with respect to cancer prevention, detection and therapy (Kennedy, 2000).

Breast reconstruction in young breast cancer patients act as significant predictor in Health-Related Quality of Life. The data shows that women with breast reconstruction show significantly less stress, anxiety and better mental health than those who have not done this procedure. Thus, stress plays a vital part in determining the complications of disease (Fanakidou *et al.*, 2018). Stress exposure possesses a vital part in determining the etiology of breast cancer. Physiological studies expose the real connection between the two variables (Antonova *et al.*, 2011). The cancer screening and following referral for psychosocial interventions has been set for the continued cancer center accreditation. This method ensures that patient distress is not only detected but also treated and dealt with utmost

management (Gudenkauf & Ehlers, 2018). A mindfulness activity was performed in a research study conducted in 2015, among the young breast cancer survivors. This activity showed short duration efficiency in alleviating stress and behavioral symptoms and pro-inflammatory chemicals in breast cancer patients (Bower *et al.*, 2015).

Breast cancer is a kind of potent traumatic stress disorder that comes out with negative outcomes, for example, Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) or Post Traumatic Growth (PTG). It has been observed that a minute number of BC patients feel PTSD while other experience PTG (Parikh *et al.*, 2015). Breast cancer affected patients felt hostile effects of the treatment. According to the research in cancer and stress, stress experienced during diagnosis and treatment of breast cancer may negatively influence the women's health. The results predict that ongoing episodic and chronic stress arising shortly after the treatment are significant predictors of the deleterious symptoms appear during and after the treatment (Harris *et al.*, 2017). Social environmental plays a crucial role in determining the health status of a person. In adequate moral and social support among the women play an important role in substantial increase in mortality associated with breast cancer. Socially isolated humans possess the physiological environment that promote the tumor growth. Appreciation of the enhanced social environment coupled with moral support could improve the revelation of the patients at greater risk of poor outcomes (Hinzey *et al.*, 2016).

The metastasis is very important in development of tumor. Tumor progression is a kind of hallmark of cancer which is accountable for significant hoard of cancer associated deaths worldwide. The mechanism of formation of secondary tumor in a part of body that is located at a distant site from the primary tumor, is defined as metastasis. The development and progression of metastasis require that cancer cells shift from their primary site and locate at a distant site, circulate in blood, tolerate blood pressure inside the blood vessels, adjust to the new surroundings and evade the immune cells (Fares *et al.*, 2020). The process of Epithelial to Mesenchymal Transition (EMT), which is very important mechanism in this regard. Hoffman *et al.* (2018), outlined that EMT possesses an important phase in guiding cell morphogenesis. Prominently, the

decline of E-cadherin proves as an important prognostic determinant factor in many kinds of carcinomas. E cadherin is a transmembrane component, is critical for function of both actin cytoskeleton and cell adhesion process. To cite an example, CDH1 contributes to cell adhesion process through calcium dependent interactions (Lee *et al.*, 2014; Piotrowski-Daspit *et al.*, 2016).

Local invasion is another kind of integral process, during which malignant affected cells denature the basal lamina, a kind of extracellular matrix specially designed in organizing and segregating epithelial cells from stroma. The matrix has an important phase in membrane signaling and acts as a growth factor. Moreover, the mechanism is vital in tumor progression that covers the traversal of tumor affected cells through blood vessels, thus permits its invasion to the blood stream. Following this mechanism, tumor affected cells are subjected towards extravasation, which is a type of infiltration as depicted in the illustration 1.1. In addition, the development of pre-metastatic niche possesses a vital phase in formation of suitable environment for the progression of cancer. This part holds potential significance, which in turn reveals either the success or failure of metastasis (Arvelo *et al.*, 2016). The macrophage origin of metastasis can also be used to portray a novel insight for the therapeutic management. Hence, metastasis involves a series of steps taking place in a measured and organized approach (Seyfried & Huysentruyt, 2013).

The *FKBP5* is an important gene that is involved in stress response and Glucocorticoid Receptor (GR) signaling. It is a protein coding gene that belongs to the family of FK-506 protein, acts as co-chaperon which modulates the folding and activity of associated proteins. It interacts with the protein such as Heat-Shock protein 90 (HSP 90), co-chaperon, P23 of steroid receptors to form protein complex. Several studies presented that the interaction of FKBP5 protein with this complex reduces the association of GR and dynein protein. This leads to delay in nuclear localization of GR complex to the nucleus; consequently, inhibiting trans-activation and trans-repression (Zannas *et al.*, 2016).

FKBP5 mRNA directly influences the process of GR complex by reducing binding affinity of cortisol with GR. Cortisol is another important factor with aspect of

stress response as it is activated by interacting with GR and leads to regulation of biological responses such as increased blood glucose level, sweating, heart beat and blood pressure. This study indicates an integral phase in developing *FKBP5* a potential stress associated biomarker of cortisol activity in the patients undergoing chemotherapy (Bancos *et al.*, 2021).

FKBP4 is another important gene associated with stress regulation by interacting with the protein complex HSP-90, GR and *FKBP5*. This interaction displaces *FKBP5* protein and *FKBP4* protein takes its place and become the part of the protein complex (Zong *et al.*, 2021). This exchange causes signal transduction and interaction with dynein protein that promotes nuclear localization. Compared to *FKBP5* protein, which reduces the contact of the protein complex with transport protein such as dynein as illustrated in figure 1.2; consequently, delaying nuclear localization and suppressing gene expression. Hence, these two proteins work in an opposite manner and that's how stress is regulated inside the cell (Davies *et al.*, 2002).

The hormone activated transcription factor is a kind of protein which is stimulated by a hormonally activated movement to the site of nucleus. To cite an example in figure 1.3, GR is collected in cytosolic fraction of cells as a complex oligomeric compound, which contains a molecule of receptor and two molecules of heat shock proteins in the absence of hormone (Davies *et al.*, 2002). *PHLPP1* is a kind of gene that is located in 18q 21.33 that is intricately involved in circadian pathways and bears module such as pH region or leucine rich enzyme domain such as phosphatase. It also possesses modified polyglutamine motif repeat at carboxyl terminal location. The disruption in circadian rhythm such as body temperature, sleep awake cycle and cortisol secretion, frequently characterize mood disorders (Anbazhagan *et al.*, 2008). Mood is defined as ubiquitous or sustained feeling or emotion that not only affects the person's behavior but also his perception. Bipolar mood disorder is the kind of disorder that affects the person behavior in broader aspects. Bipolar mood disorder is a type of complex mood disorder which is recognized by the combination of bipolar mania, hypomanic and depression-linked episodes, with significant sub-syndromal symptoms that commonly present in between the prominent mood episodes. It has been found to be associated

with severe medical and psychiatric morbidity, high level of functional disability and compromised quality of life. This is extremely true of bipolar disorder type 1 that involves manic episode occurring at least one lifetime episode. Compared to type 2 disorder that involves at least one manic episode and a major depression episode (Jain & Mitra, 2022).

FKBP5 now exists at the nucleus of research regarding stress related diseases, which has led towards the comprehending of it protein and its functions. Its expression in mice and monkeys has helped the scientists in understanding the effects of the protein in vivo (O'Leary *et al.*, 2013).

PHLPP1 is considered to be a vital factor in metastatic melanoma. The members of Pleckstrin homology region or domain leucine rich repeat protein ser-thr specialized phosphatase family can modulate AKT activation. It has an integral role in cell proliferation and survival by dephosphorylating specific serine residues in hydrophobic moiety. It has been observed in a study that its expression was significantly reduced or lost and correlation was found with metastatic potential in melanoma. Induced expression of this gene is found to be prominently associated with inhibition of cell propagation, colony formation, and migration in soft agar. Thus, the data from the current study indicates that it acts as tumor suppressor through its phosphatase activity by removing phosphorus from the region required for tumor progression (Yu *et al.*, 2018).

In another study it has been scrutinized that *PHLPP1* act as tumor alleviator in prostate cancer. It basically serves as an AKT- inactivating phosphatase and function as a tumor suppressor. It has also been found that Co-deletion of *PHLPP1* and *TP53* is highly restricted to the metastatic disease. Similarly, loss of *PHLPP1* gene is found to be associated with lymphadenopathy. These observations led to evaluate the tumor suppressive role of the gene and was determined that it was very sensitive and delicate to the degree of AKT signaling pathway (Chen *et al.*, 2012).

Recent study indicated that epigenetic alteration of genome is a primary factor associated with changes in base pairs. These modifications such as DNA methylation, chromatic remodeling and even changes in non-coding RNAs such as mi-RNA govern the landscape and result of cell fate without alteration to the DNA sequences. Irregularities in modifications

such as methylation can lead towards deleterious effects such as tumor. It has been showed that a typical methylation can cause irregular Wnt activation through elevated promotor methylation and following suppression of Wnt blockers such as Wnt Inhibitory Factor 1 (*WIF-1*) and *AXIN2*, which is linked with breast and colorectal cancer. It has been observed that aberrant methylation in Wnt negative regulators such as Naked Cuticle Homologue1 (*NKK1*) lead towards gastric cancer (Toh *et al.*, 2017). In addition, post translational modification of histone determine which part of the genome are transcriptionally active or inactive. Hence, epigenetics is a crucial and common factor among breast cancer patients. Abnormal histone modifications with integrated DNA hyper methylation is linked with epigenetic silencing of tumor alleviator genes and genomic instability (Huang *et al.*, 2011).

Moreover, abnormal methylation on CpG island is prominent epigenetic changes in human cancers and this mechanism is catalyzed by enzymes such as DNA methyl transferases such as *DNMT1* and *DNMT3a*, and *DNMT3b*. In this study, the deregulated methylation of genomic region encoding miRNA-124a in breast cancer and to evaluate their relationship between pathological properties of tumors together with expression levels of *DNMT1* and *DNMT3a*, and *DNMT3b*. With aspect of *DNMT* expression, no association was observed between *DNMT1* and *DNMT3a* and promotor methylation of any tested micro-RNA. However, a significant correlation was found between *DNMT3b* overexpression and hyper methylation of miRNA-124a. It indicates that the miRNA-124a1, miRNA-124a2 and miRNA-124a3 are normally methylated by enzymes, in breast cancer and play an integral role in tumor progression and aggressively. Hence, it can be easily said that methylation of the mentioned micro-RNA genes significantly correlated with advanced tumor progression in breast cancer patients (Ben Gacem *et al.*, 2014). It has been reported in a study conducted in Italy that cortisol levels were revealed to be raised in cancer patients (Mazzoccoli *et al.*, 2012). Similarly, it has been revealed in a study implemented in Russia, that cortisol levels in cancer patients were found to be elevated than healthy control group (Bezverkhia *et al.*, 1989). In addition, cortisol levels in oral squamous cancer patients were enhanced compared to control group (Sharma *et al.*, 2018). Keeping in view importance and significance

of *FKBP5*, our study is aimed to explore the relationship between chemotherapy patients and *FKBP5* and evaluating the cortisol level in the serum of cancer patients and comparing with control group.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Ethical Approval

After the approval of Ethical Review Committee (ERC-118-2022-; 11-11-2022) and Institutional review board (IRB-417/01-2023-; 19-01-2023) of The Forman Christian College (A Chartered University), the study was conducted.

Sampling

The clinical sampling involves patient with a specific disease or a condition. In general, clinical sampling includes multiple factors associated with internal and external validity of research methods. In clinical study, we define population as a group of people who have same characteristic or they share a common disease. To exemplify, if we are conducting study on Breast Cancer, it will be laborious to select samples of Breast Cancer (BC) from all over the world (Elfil & Negidia, 2017). The BC patients at Mayo Hospital Lahore and Jinnah Hospital Lahore, with their consent, were selected and their 5 ml blood was withdrawn by trained clinical staff at the hospital facility. The half of the blood was collected in EDTA coated Vials and remaining blood was taken in Gel and Clot Activator Tube/Gel vials for serum extraction. The samples were transferred to the university on the same day for Laboratory analysis.

RNA extraction

RNA extraction was performed following the protocols described in Biorepository (n.d.) and Rio et al. (2010). The step-by-step procedure is as follows:

- A total of 500 μ l of blood and 750 μ l of TRIzol® were combined in an eppendorf tube, which was kept on ice. The mixture was then homogenized by vortexing and then incubating at room temperature for 5 minutes.
- Subsequently, 250 μ l of chloroform was added to each sample, gently mixed by hand, and vortexed. The samples were further kept at room temperature for 5 to 10 minutes.
- The samples were then subjected to be centrifuged at 16060 g for 15 minutes at 4°C.

- Following centrifugation, three distinct layers were formed: the top aqueous layer containing the desired RNA, the middle layer containing genomic DNA and denatured proteins, and a lower organic phase.
- The samples were kept on ice, and the aqueous layer containing the RNA was carefully isolated and transferred to a new Eppendorf tube.
- To precipitate the RNA, 500 μ l of chilled isopropanol was added to each tube, mixed gently by hand, and incubated for 10 minutes at room temperature.
- The samples were then centrifuged at 18626 g for 15 minutes at 4°C, results in the formation of a pellet containing the RNA.
- The supernatant was discarded, and subsequent washing steps were executed.
- Then the washing of RNA pallet was done by adding 200 μ l of 75% ethanol, followed by centrifugation at 6082 g for 2 minutes. The ethanol was then discarded. This washing step was repeated at least twice. Subsequently, the tubes were left open to air dry for 5 to 10 minutes. Finally, 30 μ l of nuclease-free water or TE buffer was added to store the extracted RNA.

Gel Electrophoresis

The gel electrophoresis procedure was done according to the protocol explained by Lee et al. (2012). A 1.5% gel was prepared using 1x TAE buffer and placed on a casting tray. The gel was operated at 80 volts for 40 minutes, and the resulting bands were visualized using a Gel Doc for further analysis. The step-by-step procedure is as follows:

- To prepare 1.5% agarose gel, 100 ml of 1x TAE buffer was used.
- A total of 1.5 g of agarose was added to 1x TAE (100 ml) buffer in a conical flask.
- The mixture was thoroughly mixed using a stirrer, and then heated in a microwave oven for 2 minutes.
- After heating, the solution was let to cool down at room temperature for 1 minute.
- Next, 2 μ l of Safe Green™ Loading Dye or Ethidium bromide was added to the solution.

- The solution was added to a gel tank to solidify the gel, and combs were fixed into the solution.
- After 25 minutes, the PCR products and a ladder (1 KB) were loaded into the wells of the gel.
- The gel was then operated at 80 volts for 40 minutes.
- The resulting products were visualized using a UV light source, such as a Gel Doc.

cDNA Synthesis

The cDNA synthesis was executed through the use of Thermo Scientific Revert Aid Strand Synthesis cDNA senses kit number SM0311, by following the instructions explained by Li et al. (2012).

The kit reagents were thawed, centrifuged properly while placing them on ice before starting the procedure. The table 3.5.1 shows to reagents added to the autoclaved PCR tubes while performing the procedure on ice.

The prepared mixture was undergone through a short spin in a centrifuge to ensure proper mixing. In the case of cDNA synthesis using oligo dT primers, the reaction mixture in PCR tubes was heated at 42°C for 60 minutes. On the other hand, for random hexamer primer-based cDNA synthesis, the reaction mixture was first heated at 25°C for 5 minutes, which is then subjected to be followed by 60 minutes at 42°C. The mixture was treated at a high temperature of 70°C for 5 minutes to stop the reaction. The resulting cDNA was then kept at -20°C for subsequent experiments or at -80°C for longer duration.

Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

The PCR procedure was executed for DNA amplification process using gene specific primers for DNA amplification. Using the UCSC genome browser, the design of this primer was based on the melting temperature and GC content. European genomics LLC was used for ordering of gene specific primers and they were kept at -20°C. The table 3.6.1 provides the names of gene primers with their corresponding DNA sequences.

The Polymerase chain reaction was performed in sterile PCR tubes according to the conditions as illustrated in table 3.7.2. The PCR mixture was prepared sufficient for intended use. The quantities for the PCR reaction are listed in the table.

Normalization Process Utilizing β -Actin Primer

PCR sterile tubes were placed on ice and the reaction mixture was prepared. The material elucidated in the table 3.7.1 below explains the precise measurement of specific ingredients involving PCR process.

The working solution 10 micromolar was prepared from the stock of 100 micromolar using dilution. This step was taken to eliminate or minimize the chances of contamination in the master stock solution.

The analysis of PCR products was performed using gel electrophoresis. A 1.5% gel was prepared using 1x TAE buffer and then placed on a casting tray. The gel was operated at 80 volts for 40 minutes, and the resulting bands were visualized using a Gel Doc for further analysis.

Serum Extraction

Serum, which is the liquid portion of blood devoid of cells and clotting factors (Truck et al., 2009), was analyzed and extracted as it contains our desired gene in its expressed form. The serum extraction from blood samples was performed following the protocol outlined below:

- The 3ml of blood was taken in a gel vial
- The vial was then Centrifuged at 3421 g for 20 minutes.
- The top layer was Isolated and poured into Eppendorf tubes, and stored them at -80 °C for future use.

RESULTS

Figure 4.1: Graphical representation of material and methodology

Table 4.1: Demography of patients

Characteristics	Patients (n)
Number of patients	35
Median age, years	50
Range	27-75
Sex	
Male	4
Female	31
Disease	
Other cancer patients	9
Breast cancer patients	26
Radiotherapy	
Yes	17
No	18
Chemotherapy	
Yes	32
No	3
Hormone therapy	
Yes	21
No	14
Tumor grade	
I	8
II	12
III	15

4.1. Extracted RNA Results

Table 4.1.1. Nucleic acid concentration of extracted RNA samples

Samples ID	260/280	Concentration (ng/μl)	Samples ID	260/280	Concentration (ng/μl)
S001	1.81	297	S0019	1.8	345
S002	1.87	387	S0020	1.87	217
S003	1.80	425	S0021	1.70	597
S004	1.81	559	S0022	1.78	233
S005	1.69	412	S0023	1.74	417
S006	1.90	229	S0024	1.86	519
S007	1.79	345	S0025	1.82	512
S008	1.8	377	S0026	1.78	366
S009	1.81	461	S0027	1.71	343
S0010	1.91	455	S0028	1.81	226
S0011	1.87	243	S0029	1.78	376
S0012	1.89	348	S0030	1.91	670
S0013	1.8	419	S0031	1.86	655
S0014	1.75	389	S0032	1.79	421
S0015	1.89	577	S0033	1.83	210
S0016	1.80	206	S0034	1.69	198
S0017	1.82	218	S0035	1.81	252
S0018	1.73	399			

RNA extraction and cDNA synthesis was done according to the procedure described in 3.3 content, and 3.5 content, respectively. 1 kb ladder was added into the well to know the size of our amplified product that were put into the wells. The Gel electrophoresis of control and patients group was done and visualized on gel doc. The extracted RNA is shown in figures 4.1.1 and 4.1.2.

Figure 4.1.1: Analysis of RNA extraction with GeneRuler 1 kb ladder in 1st well and RNA control samples in other wells on gel doc.

Figure 4.1.2: Analysis of RNA extraction with GeneRuler 1 kb ladder in 1st well and RNA patient's samples in other wells on gel doc.

4.2. PCR of control groups

The beta actin of healthy control groups was analyzed on gel electrophoresis after undergoing PCR. β -actin is

a kind of housekeeping gene that is expressed ubiquitously throughout the body cells as shown in picture 4.2.1.

Figure 4.2.2: PCR of *FKBP5* of control group is analyzed on gel electrophoresis with GeneRuler 1 kb in 1st well and PCR products in remaining wells

Figure 4.2.1: PCR of β -actin of control group is analyzed on gel electrophoresis with GeneRuler 1 kb in 1st well and PCR products in remaining wells
The size of beta actin product is 223 base pairs as confirmed through Insilco PCR on UCSC genome

browser. Similarly, the PCR of the control group containing *FKBP5* primers, is done and it is broadly expressed in fat, lymph nodes and thyroid tissue. Its PCR is visualized on gel doc against GeneRuler 1 kb ladder as illustrated in figure 4.1.1.

The size of *FKBP5* PCR product is 222 base pairs as confirmed through Insilco PCR on UCSC genome browser. The PCR product of *FKBP5* is shown in figure 4.1.2.

4.3. PCR of patients
 The PCR of patients group beta actin was done according to conditions defined in table 3.7. The size of beta actin product is 223 base pairs as confirmed through Insilco PCR on UCSC genome browser. The PCR products of β -actin is shown in figures 4.4.1 and 4.4.2.

Figure 4.3.1: PCR of β -actin of cancer patients through Gel electrophoresis with GeneRuler 1 kb in 1st well and PCR products in remaining wells

Figure 4.3.2: Analysis of PCR of patient's β -actin through Gel electrophoresis with GeneRuler 1 kb in 1st well and PCR products (19-35 samples) in remaining wells.

Similarly, the PCR of the patients group containing *FKBP5* primers, is done and it is broadly expressed in fat, lymph nodes and thyroid tissue. Its PCR is visualized on gel doc against 1 K bp ladder as observed in figure 4.4.3 and 4.4.4.

4.4. Real time PCR and ELISA

qPCR was done for quantification of gene expression with the same protocol defined in the content 3.3. The results for the expression of *FKBP5* of patients and control are illustrated in the form of bar chart below. To evaluate the concentration of serum cortisol, ELISA was done through the CALBIOTECH kit containing catalogue No. C0368S. The procedure for the ELISA is written below.

- 25 µl of cortisol standards, control and samples of serum were placed into the holder.
- 50 µl of reagent biotin was transferred to the wells.

- 100 µl conjugate of cortisol enzyme was added to all the wells and mixed thoroughly for 10 seconds.
- The incubation was then done for 60 minutes at room temperature.
- The liquid was eliminated from all the wells and then washing was done thrice with 300 µl of 1x washing buffer
- 100 µl of substrate (TMB) was poured into the wells and incubation was executed for 15 minutes.
- 50 µl of stop solution was then added to all wells and mixing was done gently.
- Absorbance was then read at 430 nm on plate reader in under 20 minutes after adding stop solution. The absorbance for control and unknown samples was noted from the curve.

Figure. 4.4.1: Comparison of *FKBP5* expression level between control and patients group.

The figure 4.5.1 indicates that there exists a difference between *FKBP5* expression level between control and patients’ group. But it only gives us hint about nature of data. For the proper decision we

must go for hypothesis testing to decide whether there exists a significant difference in patients’ group or not. Similarly, the results for the cortisol patients and control are illustrated in the form of bar chart below.

Figure. 4.4.2: Comparison of cortisol levels between control and patients' group.

The figure 4.5.2 indicates that there exists a prominent difference between cortisol level between control and patients' group. But it only gives us hint about nature of data. For the proper decision we must go for hypothesis testing to decide whether there exists a significant difference in patients' group or not.

To find correlation between *FKBP5* expression and cortisol concentration, first we need to evaluate whether the data comes from population that follows normal distribution or not. We will analyze the assumption of whether to go with spearman or Pearson coefficient of correlation through normality testing; The level of significance is defined by alpha (0.05).

- Ho: Data results from population that follows normal probability.
 - Ha: Data results from population that do not follows normal probability.
2. Significance level: Alpha=0.05
 3. Statistics: Normality testing analyze> descriptive> explore
 4. Calculations: Normality testing

Table 4.4.1: Normality testing to evaluate the correlation analysis between cortisol level and FKBP5 expression

	NORMALITY					
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
FKBP5 expression	.276	34	<.001	.734	34	<.001
Cortisol concentration (µg/dl)	.158	34	.031	.945	34	.085

If p value is less than 0.05, it means Ho is neglected, and Ha is accepted, which indicates that data comes from population that does not follow normal distribution. Keeping in view of SPSS normality test, the level of significance came out be <0.001 for FKBP5 expression (from shapiro-wilk test), which is more preferable), given in table 4.4.1.

- P value for FKBP5 expression (<0.001) < 0.05 as indicated from the table 4.4.1, it means we may reject

Ho and Ha is true and accepted, so data comes from the population that do not follows normal distribution irrespective of what descriptive stats says. It means it is not only true for sample but also for population.

- P value (from shapiro-wilk test) for cortisol level 0.085 is greater than 0.05, it means Ho is true and Ha is rejected, so data comes from the population that follows normal distribution irrespective of what descriptive stats says.

Table 4.4.2: Correlation analysis to find the suitable test

		Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Interval by Interval	Pearson's R	.115	.135	.654	.518 ^c
Ordinal by Ordinal	Spearman Correlation	.077	.178	.435	.667 ^c
N of Valid Cases		34			

Since p value (0.667) > alpha as observed from the table 4.4.2, we may not reject Ho, which indicates that no correlation exists between FKBP5 expression and cortisol level.

Similarly, we will find the correlation between cortisol level and tumor grades. Since, P value (from shapiro-wilk test) for cortisol level 0.085 is greater than 0.05, it means Ho is true and Ha is rejected, so data comes from the population that follows normal

distribution irrespective of what descriptive stats says. Now, we need to run normality test for tumor grades.

Ho: Tumor grades and cortisol levels are independent of each other
 Ha: Correlation exists between tumor grades and cortisol level

Table 4.4.3: Normality testing to evaluate the nature of data

	NORMALITY					
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Cortisol concentration (µg/dl)	.158	34	.031	.945	34	.085
Tumor grades	.278	34	<.001	.779	34	<.001

p value (from Shapiro-wilk test) for tumor grades comes out to be <0.01 as depicted from the table

4.4.3 which is less than 0.05, it means H_a is true and H_0 is rejected, so data comes from the population that do not follows normal distribution irrespective of what descriptive stats says. Since, one variable is normal and other not normal so we will opt for spearman correlation coefficient to find relatedness between the variables.

Figure. 4.4.3: Comparison of expression level between low and high tumor grades patients the descriptive

stats in figure 4.5.3 indicate that there exists a prominent difference in expression level between high tumor grades and low tumor grades patients. But it only gives us hint about nature of data. For the proper decision we must go for hypothesis testing to decide whether there exists a correlation between tumor grades and cortisol level or not.

Table 4.4.4: p value to find correlation between tumor grades and cortisol level
SYMMETRIC MEASURES

		Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Interval by Interval	Pearson's R	.757	.058	6.544	<.001 ^c
Ordinal by Ordinal	Spearman Correlation	.758	.064	6.565	<.001 ^c
N of Valid Cases		34			

Since p value of spearman correlation coefficient is (<0.001) < alpha as observed from the table 4.4.4, we may reject H_0 , which indicates that correlation exists between tumor grades and cortisol level.

Now, we will look for the hypothesis testing for whether there is significant difference exists between cortisol levels between control group and patients' group and likewise for expression levels.

H_0 : The average of cortisol levels in male group = The average of cortisol levels in female group

H_a : The average of cortisol levels in male group \neq The average of cortisol levels in female group

The both variables are entirely independent of each other. Now, we need to find normality between the two variables.

Table 4.4.5: Normality testing to evaluate the nature of cortisol data
NORMALITY

Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.

Patients Cortisol concentration (µg/dl)	.242	10	.101	.914	10	.312
Control Cortisol (µg/dl)	.171	10	.200*	.920	10	.355

Since data from both groups comes from population that follows normal distribution, we will now go for variances testing as indicated from table 4.4.5.

Ho: Variances in cortisol level of patients in male group = Variances in cortisol level of patients in female group

Ha: Variances in cortisol level of patients in male group \neq Variances in cortisol level of patients in female group

Independent Samples Test											
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances				t-test for Equality of Means				95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	One-Sided p	Two-Sided p	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Cortisol patients (ug/dl)	Equal variances assumed	.842	.366	-.106	32	.458	.916	-.09067	.85546	-1.83318	1.65185
	Equal variances not assumed			-.131	4.528	.451	.901	-.09067	.69017	-1.92196	1.74063
Cortisol control (ug/dl)	Equal variances assumed	3.642	.093	-1.981	8	.041	.083	-1.8286	.9231	-3.9572	.3000
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.745	7.982	.013	.025	-1.8286	.6661	-3.3652	-.2920

Figure 4.4.4: Variances to evaluate the significance of cortisol levels in cancer patients

Since, p value is greater than alpha for cortisol levels in patients as given in table 4.4.4, we may not reject Ho and likewise for control group. Therefore, we conclude that Variances in cortisol level of patients in male group = Variances in cortisol level of patients in female group. Hence, the data from cortisol levels in patients' group is not significant.

Ho: The mean of FKBP5 expression in male group = The mean of FKBP5 expression in female group

Ha: The mean of FKBP5 expression in male group \neq The mean of FKBP5 expression in female group

Table 4.4.6: Normality testing to evaluate the nature of data
NORMALITY

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
FKBP5 expression of patients	.166	10	.200 [*]	.942	10	.572
FKBP5 expression of control	.177	10	.200 [*]	.925	10	.403

Since data from both groups comes from population that follows normal distribution as mentioned in table 4.4.6, we will now go for variances testing.

Ho: Variances in FKBP5 expression of patients in male group = Variances in

FKBP5 expression of patients in female group

Ha: Variances in FKBP5 expression of patients in male group \neq Variances in FKBP5 expression of patients in female group

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means							
		F	Sig.	t	df	Significance		Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						One-Sided p	Two-Sided p			Lower	Upper
FKBP5 expression	Equal variances assumed	.175	.679	-.289	32	.387	.774	-.1197551850	.41385347095	-.9627471193	.72323674929
	Equal variances not assumed			-.349	4.412	.372	.743	-.1197551850	.34322881925	-1.038610023	.79909965298
FKBP5 expression	Equal variances assumed	1.656	.234	-1.528	8	.083	.165	-.2787726440	.18245747786	-.6995203424	.14197505449
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.284	7.377	.027	.054	-.2787726440	.12207367836	-.5644687549	.00692346704

Figure 4.4.5.: Variances to evaluate the significance of gene expression levels in cancer patients

Since, p value is greater than alpha, according to figure 4.5.5, for expression level in patients as given in pic, we may not reject Ho and likewise for control group. Therefore, we conclude that Variances in FKBP5 expression of patients in male group = Variances in

FKBP5 expression of patients in female group. Hence, the data from FKBP5 expression levels in patients group is not significant

Figure 4.4.6. *FKBP5* expression illustrating survival probability

Kaplan-Meier plotter indicate the *FKBP5* expression level in cancer patients as significant as p value came out be 0.0062 which is less than alpha (0.05). Thus,

it shows that patients with raised expression of *FKBP5* indicates high survival probability.

Figure 4.4.7: Comparison of average of cortisol level between high tumor grades vs low tumor grades patients

The figure 4.5.7 show that there appears to be prominent difference between cortisol levels of high tumor grades patients compared to low tumor grades patients, which indicates that patients with high tumor grades are under more stress than low tumor grades patients.

DISCUSSION

Stress is a sort of important risk factor that leads to the development and progression of major depression among the people (Ising et al., 2019). The *FKBP5* is an important gene that is linked in stress response and Glucocorticoid Receptor (GR) signaling. It is a protein coding gene that belongs to the family of FK-506 protein, acts as co-chaperon which modulates the folding and activity of associated proteins. It interacts with the proteins such as Heat-Shock protein 90 (HSP 90), co-chaperon and P23 of steroid receptors to form protein complex. Several studies presented that the interaction of *FKBP5* protein with this complex reduces the association of GR and dynein protein. This leads to delay in nuclear localization of GR complex to the nucleus; consequently, inhibiting trans-activation and trans-repression (Zannas et al., 2016).

FKBP5 mRNA directly influences the action of GR complex through reducing the binding affinity of cortisol with GR. Cortisol is another important factor with aspect of stress response as it is activated by interacting with GR and leads to regulation of biological responses such as increased blood glucose level, sweating, heart beat and blood pressure. This research indicates an integral step in forming *FKBP5* a potential stress associated indicator and biomarker of cortisol activity in the patients undergoing chemotherapy (Bancos et al., 2021).

Our findings reveal that *FKBP5* expression increases under stress situations such as during cancer. It relates us to study conducted in 2011, which indicated that *FKBP5* is over expressed in prostate cancer patients (Li et al., 2011). Similarly, it has also been observed in study designed in 2021, that *FKBP5* expression is enhanced in human papillary thyroid carcinoma compared to healthy control (Gao et al., 2021).

Our data indicates that *FKBP5* expression increases under stress situations such as cancer disease. Keeping

in view this finding, let us discuss the analysis which was carried out in 2016 to evaluate the stress related gene expression of *FKBP5*. It was shown that its expression increases under stress situations such as cancer. It was also found to be associated with increased body weight. It is revealed that stress has a critical role in enhancing gene expression of stress related gene such as *FKBP5* (Zannas et al., 2016).

In addition, research was conducted at Department of Respiratory Medicine in China to analyze *FKBP5* expression in cancer patients, that showed that its expression was increased in patients affected with Hepatocellular Carcinoma (HCC), which is most prominent type of liver cancer (Zhang et al., 2021). According to the study in 2009, *FKBP5* is highly expressed in brain cancer prostate cancer, head cancer, neck cancer and melanoma. On the other hand, its expression is also appearing to be reduced in pancreatic cancer and colon cancer (Pei et al., 2009).

Furthermore, scientists in Japan devised research to explore the stress associated *FKBP5* gene in breast cancer patients. Their study revealed that *FKBP5* expression was enhanced in breast cancer patients (Habara et al., 2022). In addition, a study was carried out to explore the gene expression under stress situation such as breast cancer. *FKBP5* expression was observed to be elevated in breast cancer patients which further supports our results (Wellberg et al., 2017).

Our study illustrated no correlation in *FKBP5* expression in cancer patients compared to control. It highlights the research implemented in 2023, that also revealed no significant correlation in *FKBP5* expression in cancer patients compared to control patients (Xiaou et al., 2023). Compared to the study conducted in China where *FKBP5* expression levels were evaluated in cancer patients. it was showed that *FKBP5* expression was positively correlated with cancer patients (Gao et al., 2021). Similarly in China, study was conducted to scrutinize the relation between *FKBP5* expression and cancer patients. It was indicated that *FKBP5* expression was related with cancer disease (Xiao et al., 2023).

Our data states that there exists no significance in *FKBP5* expression in cancer patients with regard to gender. This is also true for the research analysis conducted in Lahore, that revealed that *FKBP5*

expression is non-significant in breast cancer patients (Fiaz *et al.*, 2022).

Our research reveals that cortisol level increases under stress conditions. Stress can be of any type such as fight or flight response (Emergency situations) or disease condition. Our finding is associated with a study conducted in 2014 to examine the serum cortisol level in stress situation. It was found the stress enhances the cascades of events that promotes the enhanced production of stress hormone (Cortisol) (Nicolas *et al.*, 2014).

Similarly, a study illustrated the pathological manifestation of stress and cortisol level. The study indicate that stress leads to series of reactions that provoke the psychiatric, inflammatory and physiological effects on body that are associated with increases level of cortisol hormone. This finding paves the way for the scientists to explore the therapeutic agents that alters the physiological responses linked with stress associated disorders (Chrousos and Gold, 1992). Furthermore, an analysis was carried out in 2011 to evaluate the stress biology. It explained the *FKBP5* and cortisol as a biomarker for stress associated biology that may lead towards deleterious complications. Due to the significant and integrity of this stress associated gene, it has gained importance in recent sciences. The analysis explained that *FKBP5* is regulator of cortisol production. It also states that stress increases the production of cortisol due to biochemical reactions that takes place intracellularly (Stechschulte and Sanchez, 2011).

Moreover, scientists at research unit for Enzymology in Germany improvised a research based on analysis of stress releasing hormone and stress. It revealed that *FKBP5* possesses an integral role in regulating cortisol secretion in the body. It means the expressed gene has an important role in modulating not only cortisol production but stress regulation, which further improvises the way for diagnostic purposes in future (Weiwad *et al.*, 2006).

As far as cortisol levels are concerned, our study indicates that its levels are enhanced in cancer patients compared to control group but no significance was found in patients group with respect to cortisol level. It brings us to the research designed in Sweden, that

showed that cortisol levels increased in cancer patients in contrast to control group (Rasmuson *et al.*, 2001).

Similarly, serum cortisol concentration has been although observed to be enhanced in breast cancer patients keeping in mind descriptive stats but no significance was observed in patients in regard to cortisol levels (Wang *et al.*, 2023). Moreover, a study was operated in India to analyze the serum cortisol level in cancer patients, which revealed that significant difference was found in cancer patients with regard to cortisol level (Sharma *et al.*, 2018).

Our objective of the study includes the scrutinization of the *FKBP5* expression together with cortisol level under stress situation such as cancer and compare with control group. Quantitative analysis of the gene expression revealed that *FKBP5* expression increases under stress situations such as during cancer. This also indicates that its gene expression increases in the cancer patients in contrast to control group. Another revelation is associated with tumor grading and expression level. It indicated that specific gene is expressed in higher quantity in high tumor grades compared to low tumor grades patients. As far as hypothesis testing is concerned keeping in view decision rule, no significance difference was found in *FKBP5* expression with respect gender. Similarly, no significance difference was analyzed in cortisol levels of patients with respect to gender.

Kaplan-Meier plotter displays the *FKBP5* expression level in cancer patients as significant as p value came out be 0.0062 which is less than alpha (0.05). Thus, it shows that patients with greater expression of *FKBP5* indicates high survival probability. This brings us to the study implemented in Italy to scrutinize the role of *FKBP5* in predicting overall survival probability in patients suffering from Malignant Pleural Mesothelioma. It showed that its high expression is linked with high survival probability in patients with Malignant Pleural Mesothelioma. Thus, it indicates significant role of *FKBP5* expression in many types of cancer (Cugliari *et al.*, 2020)

REFERENCES

- Anbazhagan, P., Purushottam, M., Kiran Kumar, H. B., Kubendran, S., Mukherjee, O., Brahmachari, S. K., Jain, S., & Sowdhamini, R. (2008). Evolutionary analysis of PHLPP1 gene in humans and non-human primates. *Bioinformatics*, 2(10), 471-474. <https://doi.org/10.6026/97320630002471>
- Antonova, L., Aronson, K., & Mueller, C. R. (2011). Stress and breast cancer: from epidemiology to molecular biology. *Breast Cancer Res*, 13(2), 208. doi:10.1186/bcr2836
- Bancos, I., Hatipoglu, B. A., Yuen, K. C. J., Chandramohan, L., Chaudhari, S., & Moraitis, A. G. (2021). Evaluation of FKBP5 as a cortisol activity biomarker in patients with ACTH-dependent Cushing syndrome. *J Clin Transl Endocrinol*, 24, 100256. doi:10.1016/j.jcte.2021.1002561231121
- Baughman, G., Wiederrecht, G. J., Campbell, N. F., Martin, M. M., & Bourgeois, S. (1995). FKBP51, a novel T-cell-specific immunophilin capable of calcineurin inhibition. *Molecular and cellular biology*, 15(8), 4395-4402. <https://doi.org/10.1128/MCB.15.8.4395>
- Baughman, G., Wiederrecht, G. J., Chang, F., Martin, M. M., & Bourgeois, S. (1997). Tissue distribution and abundance of human FKBP51, and FK506-binding protein that can mediate calcineurin inhibition. *Biochemical and biophysical research communications*, 232(2), 437-443. <https://doi.org/10.1006/bbrc.1997.6307>
- Ben Gacem, R., Ben Abdelkrim, O., Ziadi, S., Ben Dhiab, M., & Trimeche, M. (2014). Methylation of miR-124a-1, miR-124a-2, and miR-124a-3 genes correlates with aggressive and advanced breast cancer disease. *Tumour biology : the journal of the International Society for Oncodevelopmental Biology and Medicine*, 35(5), 4047-4056. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13277-013-1530-4>
- Benz, C. C., & Yau, C. (2008). Ageing, oxidative stress and cancer: paradigms in parallax. *Nat Rev Cancer*, 8(11), 875-879. doi:10.1038/nrc2522
- Bezverkhaya, T. P., Rybakov, O. I., Komissarenko, I. V., & Verkhogliadova, L. M. (1989). [Glucocorticoids in patients with tumors of the adrenal cortex]. *Probl Endokrinol (Mosk)*, 35(1), 11-15.
- Biorepository, G. M. (n.d.). *RNA and miRNA Isolation from Human Peripheral Blood*. 23-24.
- Bower, J. E., Crosswell, A. D., Stanton, A. L., Crespi, C. M., Winston, D., Arevalo, J., . . . Ganz, P. A. (2015). Mindfulness meditation for younger breast cancer survivors: a randomized controlled trial. *Cancer*, 121(8), 1231-1240. doi:10.1002/cncr.29194
- Bryla, C. M. (1996). The relationship between stress and the development of breast cancer: a literature review. *Oncol Nurs Forum*, 23(3), 441-448
- Chen, M., Pratt, C. P., Zeeman, M. E., Schultz, N., Barry, S., Neill, A. O., Castillo-martin, M., Nowak, D. G., Naguib, A., Grace, M., Murn, J., Navin, N., Atwal, G. S., Sander, C., William, L., Cordon-cardo, C., Newton, A. C., Carver, B. S., & Lloyd, C. (2012). *progression*. 20(2), 173-186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccr.2011.07.013.I> identification
- Chrousos, G. P., & Gold, P. W. (1992). The concepts of stress and stress system disorders. Overview of physical and behavioral homeostasis. *Jama*, 267(9), 1244-1252.
- Cugliari, G., Catalano, C., Guarrera, S., Allione, A., Casalone, E., Russo, A., . . . Matullo, G. (2020). DNA Methylation of FKBP5 as Predictor of Overall Survival in Malignant Pleural Mesothelioma. *Cancers (Basel)*, 12(11). doi:10.3390/cancers12113470
- Dai, S., Mo, Y., Wang, Y., Xiang, B., Liao, Q., Zhou, M., . . . Zeng, Z. (2020). Chronic Stress Promotes Cancer Development. *Front Oncol*, 10, 1492. doi:10.3389/fonc.2020.01492

- Davies, T. H., Ning, Y. M., & Sánchez, E. R. (2002). A new first step in activation of steroid receptors: hormone-induced switching of FKBP51 and FKBP52 immunophilins. *J Biol Chem*, 277(7), 4597-4600. doi:10.1074/jbc.C100531200
- Eckerling, A., Ricon-Becker, I., Sorski, L., Sandbank, E., & Ben-Eliyahu, S. (2021). Stress and cancer: mechanisms, significance and future directions. *Nat Rev Cancer*, 21(12), 767-785. doi:10.1038/s41568-021-00395-5
- Elfil, M., & Negida, A. (2017). Sampling methods in Clinical Research; an Educational Review. *Emergency (Tehran, Iran)*, 5(1), e52.
- Fanakidou, I., Zyga, S., Alikari, V., Tsironi, M., Stathoulis, J., & Theofilou, P. (2018). Mental health, loneliness, and illness perception outcomes in quality of life among young breast cancer patients after mastectomy: the role of breast reconstruction. *Qual Life Res*, 27(2), 539-543. doi:10.1007/s11136-017-1735-x
- Fares, J., Fares, M. Y., Khachfe, H. H., Salhab, H. A., & Fares, Y. (2020). Molecular principles of metastasis: a hallmark of cancer revisited. *Signal transduction and targeted therapy*, 5(1), 28. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-020-0134-x
- Feng, Y., Spezia, M., Huang, S., Yuan, C., Zeng, Z., Zhang, L., Ji, X., Liu, W., Huang, B., Luo, W., Liu, B., Lei, Y., Du, S., Vuppapapati, A., Luu, H. H., Haydon, R. C., He, T. C., & Ren, G. (2018). Breast cancer development and progression: Risk factors, cancer stem cells, signaling pathways, genomics, and molecular pathogenesis. *Genes & diseases*, 5(2), 77-106. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gendis.2018.05.001
- Fiaz, T., Nadeem, M. S., Afzal, O., Altamimi, A. S. A., Alzarea, S. I., Almalki, W. H., . . . Mustafa, M. (2022). Peripheral mRNA Expression and Prognostic Significance of Emotional Stress Biomarkers in Metastatic Breast Cancer Patients. *Int J Mol Sci*, 23(22). doi:10.3390/ijms232214097
- Gao, Z., Yu, F., Jia, H., Ye, Z., & Yao, S. (2021). FK506-binding protein 5 promotes the progression of papillary thyroid carcinoma. *J Int Med Res*, 49(4), 3000605211008325. doi:10.1177/03000605211008325
- Gawlik, M., Moller-Ehrlich, K., Mende, M., Jovnerovski, M., Jung, S., Jabs, B., Knapp, M., & Stoeber, G. (2006). Is FKBP5 a genetic marker of affective psychosis? A case control study and analysis of disease related traits. *BMC psychiatry*, 6, 52. https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-244X-6-52
- Gudenkauf, L. M., & Ehlers, S. L. (2018). Psychosocial interventions in breast cancer survivorship care. *Breast*, 38, 1-6. doi:10.1016/j.breast.2017.11.005
- Habara, M., Sato, Y., Goshima, T., Sakurai, M., Imai, H., Shimizu, H., . . . Shimada, M. (2022). FKBP52 and FKBP51 differentially regulate the stability of estrogen receptor in breast cancer. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 119(15), e2110256119. doi:10.1073/pnas.2110256119
- Hanson, E. J. (1994). An exploration of the taken-for-granted world of the cancer nurse in relation to stress and the person with cancer. *J Adv Nurs*, 19(1), 12-20. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2648.1994.tb01045.x
- Hinze, A., Gaudier-Diaz, M. M., Lustberg, M. B., & DeVries, A. C. (2016). Breast cancer and social environment: getting by with a little help from our friends. *Breast Cancer Res*, 18(1), 54. doi:10.1186/s13058-016-0700-x
- Huang, Y., Nayak, S., Jankowitz, R., Davidson, N. E., & Oesterreich, S. (2011). *Epigenetics in breast cancer: what 's new?* 1-11.
- Hockenberry-Eaton, M., Kemp, V., & DiIorio, C. (1994). Cancer stressors and protective factors: predictors of stress experienced during treatment for childhood cancer. *Res Nurs Health*, 17(5), 351-361. doi:10.1002/nur.4770170506

- Hoffmann, C., Mao, X., Brown-Clay, J., Moreau, F., Al Absi, A., Wurzer, H., . . . Janji, B (2018). Hypoxia promotes breast cancer cell invasion through HIF-1 α -mediated up-regulation of the invadopodial actin bundling protein CSRP2. *Scientific reports*; 8(1): 1-14
- Harris, L. N., Bauer, M. R., Wiley, J. F., Hammen, C., Krull, J. L., Crespi, C. M., . . . Stanton, A. L. (2017). Chronic and episodic stress predict physical symptom bother following breast cancer diagnosis. *J Behav Med*, 40(6), 875-885. doi:10.1007/s10865-017-9855-x
- Ising, M., Maccarrone, G., Brückl, T., Scheuer, S., Hennings, J., Holsboer, F., . . . Lucae, S. (2019). FKBP5 Gene Expression Predicts Antidepressant Treatment Outcome in Depression. *Int J Mol Sci*, 20(3). doi:10.3390/ijms20030485
- Jain, A., & Mitra, P. (2022). Bipolar Affective Disorder. In *StatPearls*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Jinwal, U. K., Koren, J., 3rd, Borysov, S. I., Schmid, A. B., Abisambra, J. F., Blair, L. J., Johnson, A. G., Jones, J. R., Shults, C. L., O'Leary, J. C., 3rd, Jin, Y., Buchner, J., Cox, M. B., & Dickey, C. A. (2010). The Hsp90 cochaperone, FKBP51, increases Tau stability and polymerizes microtubules. *The Journal of neuroscience : the official journal of the Society for Neuroscience*, 30(2), 591-599. https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.4815-09.2010
- Kolak, A., Kamińska, M., Sygit, K., Budny, A., Surdyka, D., Kukiełka-Budny, B., & Burdan, F. (2017). Primary and secondary prevention of breast cancer. *Ann Agric Environ Med*, 24(4), 549-553. doi:10.26444/aaem/75943
- Kendler, K. S., Prescott, C. A., Myers, J., & Neale, M. C. (2003). The structure of genetic and environmental risk factors for common psychiatric and substance use disorders in men and women. *Arch Gen Psychiatry*, 60(9), 929-937. doi:10.1001/archpsyc.60.9.929
- Kennedy, B. J. (2000). Aging and cancer. *Oncology (Williston Park)*, 14(12), 1731-1733; discussion 1734, 1739-1740.
- Koh, J., & Kim, M. J. (2019). Introduction of a New Staging System of Breast Cancer for Radiologists: An Emphasis on the Prognostic Stage. *Korean journal of radiology*, 20(1), 69-82. https://doi.org/10.3348/kjr.2018.0231
- Lee, M.-S., Kim, S., Kim, B. G., Won, C., Nam, S. H., Kang, S., . . . Song, H. E. (2014). Snail1 induced in breast cancer cells in 3D collagen I gel environment suppresses cortactin and impairs effective invadopodia formation. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)-Molecular Cell Research*; 1843(9): 2037-2054.
- Lee, P. Y., Costumbrado, J., Hsu, C., & Kim, Y. H. (2012). Agarose Gel Electrophoresis for the Separation of DNA Fragments. *April*, 1-5. https://doi.org/10.3791/3923
- Li, L., Lou, Z., & Wang, L. (2011). The role of FKBP5 in cancer aetiology and chemoresistance. *Br J Cancer*, 104(1), 19-23. doi:10.1038/sj.bjc.6606014
- Lu, B., Jiao, Y., Wang, Y., Dong, J., Wei, M., Cui, B., Sun, Y., Wang, L., Zhang, B., Chen, Z., & Zhao, Y. (2017). A FKBP5 mutation is associated with Paget's disease of bone and enhances osteoclastogenesis. *Experimental & molecular medicine*, 49(5), e336. https://doi.org/10.1038/emm.2017.64
- Lugassy, C., & Escande, J. P. (1997). The haematogenous theory of metastasis: Récamier did not propose it. *Virchows Archiv : an international journal of pathology*, 431(5), 431. https://doi.org/10.1007/s004280050113
- Mehata, A. K., & Dahari, D. (2020). Conforming Pathophysiological State of the Animal. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 10(1), 105-110.
- Mazzoccoli, G., Giuliani, F., & Sothorn, R. B. (2012). Determination of whole body circadian phase in lung cancer patients: melatonin vs. cortisol. *Cancer Epidemiol*, 36(1), e46-53. doi:10.1016/j.canep.2011.06.005

- Nicolaidis, N. C., Charmandari, E., Chrousos, G. P., & Kino, T. (2014). Recent advances in the molecular mechanisms determining tissue sensitivity to glucocorticoids: novel mutations, circadian rhythm and ligand-induced repression of the human glucocorticoid receptor. *BMC Endocrine Disorders*, 14(1), 71. doi:10.1186/1472-6823-14-71
- O'Leary, J. C., 3rd, Zhang, B., Koren, J., 3rd, Blair, L., & Dickey, C. A. (2013). The role of FKBP5 in mood disorders: action of FKBP5 on steroid hormone receptors leads to questions about its evolutionary importance. *CNS Neurol Disord Drug Targets*, 12(8), 1157-1162
- Parikh, D., De Ieso, P., Garvey, G., Thachil, T., Ramamoorthi, R., Penniment, M., & Jayaraj, R. (2015). Post-traumatic stress disorder and post-traumatic growth in breast cancer patients—a systematic review. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev*, 16(2), 641-646. doi:10.7314/apjcp.2015.16.2.641
- Pei, H., Li, L., Fridley, B. L., Jenkins, G. D., Kalari, K. R., Lingle, W., . . . Wang, L. (2009). FKBP51 affects cancer cell response to chemotherapy by negatively regulating Akt. *Cancer Cell*, 16(3), 259-266. doi:10.1016/j.ccr.2009.07.016
- Piotrowski-Daspit, A. S., Tien, J., & Nelson, C. M. (2016). Interstitial fluid pressure regulates collective invasion in engineered human breast tumors via Snail, vimentin, and E-cadherin. *Integrative Biology*; 8(3): 319-331.
- Rasmuson, T., Ljungberg, B., Grankvist, K., Jacobsen, J., & Olsson, T. (2001). Increased serum cortisol levels are associated with high tumour grade in patients with renal cell carcinoma. *Acta Oncol*, 40(1), 83-87. doi:10.1080/028418601750071118
- Seyfried, T. N., & Huysentruyt, L. C. (2013). On the origin of cancer metastasis. *Critical reviews in oncogenesis*, 18(1-2), 43-73. <https://doi.org/10.1615/critrevoncog.v18.i1-2.40>
- Sharma, P., Sandhu, S. V., Bhandari, R., Verma, I., Bhullar, R. K., & Khangura, R. K. (2018). Estimation of cortisol levels in patients with premalignant disorders and oral squamous cell carcinoma. *J Oral Maxillofac Pathol*, 22(1), 27-34. doi:10.4103/jomfp.JOMFP_181_16
- Sharma, P., Sandhu, S. V., Bhandari, R., Verma, I., Bhullar, R. K., & Khangura, R. K. (2018). Estimation of cortisol levels in patients with premalignant disorders and oral squamous cell carcinoma. *J Oral Maxillofac Pathol*, 22(1), 27-34. doi:10.4103/jomfp.JOMFP_181_16
- Sinars, C. R., Cheung-Flynn, J., Rimerman, R. A., Scammell, J. G., Smith, D. F., & Clardy, J. (2003). Structure of the large FK506-binding protein FKBP51, an Hsp90-binding protein and a component of steroid receptor complexes. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 100(3), 868-873. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0231020100>
- Spruill, T. M. (2010). Chronic psychosocial stress and hypertension. *Curr Hypertens Rep*, 12(1), 10-16. doi:10.1007/s11906-009-0084-8
- Stechschulte, L. A., & Sanchez, E. R. (2011). FKBP51—a selective modulator of glucocorticoid and androgen sensitivity. *Curr Opin Pharmacol*, 11(4), 332-337. doi:10.1016/j.coph.2011.04.012
- Toh, T. B., Lim, J. J., & Chow, E. K. H. (2017). Epigenetics in cancer stem cells. *Molecular Cancer*, 16(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12943-017-0596-9>
- Tuck, M. K., Chan, D. W., Chia, D., Godwin, A. K., Grizzle, W. E., Krueger, K. E., Rom, W., Sanda, M., Sorbara, L., Stass, S., Wang, W., & Brenner, D. E. (2009). Standard operating procedures for serum and plasma collection: early detection research network consensus statement standard operating procedure integration working group. *Journal of proteome research*, 8(1), 113-117. <https://doi.org/10.1021/pr800545q>

- Ueyama, T., Kasamatsu, K., Hano, T., Tsuruo, Y., & Ishikura, F. (2008). Catecholamines and estrogen are involved in the pathogenesis of emotional stress-induced acute heart attack. *Ann N Y Acad Sci*, 1148, 479-485. doi:10.1196/annals.1410.079
- Wang, F., Giskeødegård, G. F., Skarra, S., Engstrøm, M. J., Hagen, L., Geisler, J., . . . Bathen, T. F. (2023). Association of serum cortisol and cortisone levels and risk of recurrence after endocrine treatment in breast cancer. *Clinical and Experimental Medicine*. doi:10.1007/s10238-023-01109-x
- Weiwad, M., Edlich, F., Kilka, S., Erdmann, F., Jarczowski, F., Dorn, M., . . . Fischer, G. (2006). Comparative analysis of calcineurin inhibition by complexes of immunosuppressive drugs with human FK506 binding proteins. *Biochemistry*, 45(51), 15776-15784. doi:10.1021/bi061616p
- Wellberg, E. A., Checkley, L. A., Giles, E. D., Johnson, S. J., Oljira, R., Wahdan-Alaswad, R., . . . Anderson, S. M. (2017). The Androgen Receptor Supports Tumor Progression After the Loss of Ovarian Function in a Preclinical Model of Obesity and Breast Cancer. *Horm Cancer*, 8(5-6), 269-285. doi:10.1007/s12672-017-0302-9
- Xiao, Y., Wang, Y., Xu, X., Jiao, X., & Huo, Y. (2023). Integrated analysis reveals potential significance of FKBP5 in the prognosis and immunity of osteoarthritis and pan-cancer. *Electronic Journal of Biotechnology*, 65, 24-44. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejbt.2023.05.002
- Yu, Y., Dai, M., Lu, A., Yu, E., & Merlino, G. (2018). PHLPP1 mediates melanoma metastasis suppression through repressing AKT2 activation. *Oncogene*, 37(17), 2225-2236. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41388-017-0061-7
- Zannas, A. S., Wiechmann, T., Gassen, N. C., & Binder, E. B. (2016). Gene-Stress-Epigenetic Regulation of FKBP5: Clinical and Translational Implications. *Neuropsychopharmacology*, 41(1), 261-274. doi:10.1038/npp.2015.235
- Zhang, C., Cui, X., Feng, L., Han, Z., Peng, D., Fu, W., & Xing, Y. (2021). The deficiency of FKBP-5 inhibited hepatocellular progression by increasing the infiltration of distinct immune cells and inhibiting obesity-associated gut microbial metabolite. *J Gastrointest Oncol*, 12(2), 711-721. doi:10.21037/jgo-21-71
- Zong, S., Jiao, Y., Liu, X., Mu, W., Yuan, X., Qu, Y., . . . Zhao, Y. (2021). FKBP4 integrates FKBP4/Hsp90/IKK with FKBP4/Hsp70/RelA complex to promote lung adenocarcinoma progression via IKK/NF-κB signaling. *Cell Death Dis*, 12(6), 602. doi:10.1038/s41419-021-03857-8